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Effects of Online Sellers E-Service Quality on the Customer Loyalty

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of online sellers' e-service quality (E-SQ) on customer loyalty among online shoppers in Cabiao, Nueva Ecija. The research is grounded in the E-S-QUAL model, emphasizes five core dimensions of service quality (efficiency, reliability, fulfillment and responsiveness, flexibility, and privacy). As online shopping continues to grow in popularity, understanding how these service dimensions influence customer behaviors such as repeat purchases, trust, and recommendations is vital for enhancing customer satisfaction and retention.

A descriptive-quantitative research design was employed to assess the relationship between e-service quality and customer loyalty. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire distributed to 100 respondents who were selected using convenience sampling. The questionnaire measured participants' perceptions of online sellers' performance across the five dimensions of E-SQ and their corresponding loyalty behaviors.

Findings revealed that respondents generally perceive online sellers positively across all five E-SQ dimensions. Privacy and efficiency received the highest ratings, indicating that customers value secure transactions and smooth service processes the most. The analysis showed a significant positive association between high levels of perceived e-service quality and customer loyalty.

The results supported the hypothesis that enhanced e-service quality leads to stronger customer loyalty in terms of repeat purchases, trust, and recommendations. The emphasis on privacy and efficiency suggests that customers are more likely to remain loyal to sellers who provide safe, reliable, and user-friendly online shopping experiences. These findings align with existing literature on the importance of service quality in digital marketplaces

1. Introduction

E-commerce is the commercial transactions of products and services through the internet using technologies such as mobile phones or computer. It has developed so fast since then though that it has only accelerated its worldwide appeal as a leading business model (Sitthipon et al., 2022). Social commerce has swiftly developed in recent years through the integration of social media in online shopping, leading to a quick shift in the way that customers interact with a brand and participate in decision-making processes in shopping. This development carries great potential for e-commerce penetration in developing countries (Attar et al., 2021). E-commerce transactions traditionally occur through specialized websites, or on specific online marketplaces as well as mobile applications that serve a specific brand, making it easy for consumers to access the products they want. Exploring the relationship between e-service quality and customer loyalty, highlighting the ongoing transformation and significance of e-commerce in the digital age (Asanprakit, S., & Kraiwanit, T. 2023),

As the e-commerce continues to expand issues with e-service quality still exist and have an impact on customer loyalty and satisfaction. Many online shoppers encounter problems like slow website performance, unresponsive customer support, security issues, and order fulfillment delays (Juwaini et al., 2022). Because of this companies find it difficult to keep customers and establish a trust in online transactions. Understanding the E-Service Quality influences customer satisfaction and customer loyalty is crucial for online retailers aiming to improve their service quality and competitive position. Making the online shopping experience seamless and reliable is one of the key issues that e-commerce businesses are challenged with. Research studies suggest that e-service quality significantly influences customer loyalty, satisfaction and trust (Muharam et al., 2021). Shoppers value a site that is easy

to navigate, secure to transact with, and that comes with prompt responsive to queries, all of which add to the shopping experience Completed with image slicer. However, inadequate service quality primarily causes to dissatisfaction, which results in low customer retention and negative word-of-mouth (Kusdibyo & Februadi, 2019). The Security and reliability issues of businesses must also be taken care of as trust also plays a mediating role between E-Service Quality and loyalty (Ashiq & Hussain, 2024).

Even though online shopping is becoming more and more popular many businesses are not optimizing these crucial service dimensions which causes a gap between what customers' expectations and what is actually provided. This research paper shows that the higher E-Service quality the more sustainable the loyalty will be, and the indirect impact of E-Service Quality on loyalty are another serious issues needed to be consider (Purwanto, 2022). This issue reinforces the need to identify which dimensions of the E-Service Quality affect high customer satisfaction level. Moreover, as organizations with higher level of digital strategy also feature more customer engagement and trust, technology and digital posture are important in molding e-commerce experience (Olaleye et al., 2021).

E-Service Quality is so competitive that online retailers face the risk that if they do not improve strategically their online E-service Quality, they will lose market share to competitors who prioritize customer-centric digital experiences. Companies need to address these problems to remain competitive in the vibrant e-commerce space. Reduced customer satisfaction and a declining customer retention result mainly from poor security, inconsistency of service quality and poor customer support (Rita et al., 2019).

Retailers need to establish a plan to enhance e-service quality, trust and finally loyalty in the era of e-retail. According to a better knowledge of how E-Service Quality influence on the consumer patterns, businesses can enhance the complete shopping experience by identify crucial fields to develop and make some focused intervention. With this point of view, the study sought to determine the effect of e-service quality of online sellers on customer loyalty of online shoppers in Cabiao, Nueva Ecija. The objective of the present research is to examine how individuals perceive e-service quality in terms of effectiveness, reliability, order fulfillment & responsiveness, flexibility, and privacy. and the direct relationship between e-service quality and loyalty towards online sellers. Through these links, this study seeks to identify the relevance between the perceived quality of e-services and customer loyalty. The research was conducted within the context of the E-S-QUAL model, a structured model to measure the overall quality of services delivered online that has been developed by Parasuraman et al. (2005).

2. Research Method

2.1 Research Design

This study made an assessment of the "Effects of Online Sellers' E-Service Quality on Customer Loyalty." To accomplish this, the researchers employed a descriptive and quantitative research design. Descriptive method of research involves the careful and systematic gathering and analysis of empirical data to develop knowledge. While the descriptive models can be of different natures, they all depend on the researcher's special capacities for data gathering and interpretation.

2.2 Participants

The researchers used Convenience sampling (a non-probability sampling technique), and the respondents were identified in Cabiao. This site was selected for convenience and the availability of potential subjects meeting the study inclusion criteria. With this sampling method, the researchers guaranteed that the result of the selection was adequately distributed. In this case, 100 respondents are adequate to ensure sufficient data can be collected and handled without deviating from the aims of the study.

2.3 Instrumentation

A researcher-made questionnaire was developed as the primary instrument for data collection in order to examine the effects of online sellers' e-service quality on customer loyalty. To ensure the clarity, reliability, and validity of the instrument, the questionnaire was pre-tested among 30 individuals who did not participate in the final survey. The response from the pre-test was utilized to enhance the clarity of the items and the language of the items. The resulting questionnaire was organized into three main parts to obtain valuable information in connection with the study objectives.

Part 1 of the tool covered demographic information. This category encompassed important background information, such as age, sex, civil status, frequency of using the Internet for shopping, and where individuals order items most often. These dimensions were important in identifying who the respondents were and how certain similarities or regularities could be made for the individual traits and interacting with online. Part 2 is the respondent's perceptions of online sellers' e-service quality. To show the respondent's level of agreement, the researchers used the 5-point Likert scale, where (1) strongly disagree; (2) disagree; (3) Somewhat Agree; (4) agree; and (5) strongly agree. Part 3 is the customer loyalty affects by the online sellers e-service quality.

2.4 Validation of Instrument

The instruments underwent contextual validation, examination, changes, and other actions as judged essential to establish validity. To gather data from the respondents, a questionnaire was chosen.

2.5 Data Gathering Procedures

The researchers sought formal approval to conduct the study titled "Effects of Online Sellers' E-Service Quality on Customer Loyalty." After the approval, the researchers handed the questionnaires to the chosen respondents who live in Cabiao, Nueva Ecija, and are aged 18 to 35 years old, who engage in online shopping.

Questionnaire procedure the questionnaire was administered in the street for the entire population, and researchers explained verbally to participants what they had to do in order to complete it. Appropriate time was provided to the respondents to complete all sections of the questionnaire at their ease.

2.6 Analysis of Data

The data gathered in this study was arranged and used the research design as a guide. This include using of Likert scale, weighted mean, and Spearman's rho correlation as instruments for data collection, interpretation, and analysis. Each of these tools served a specific purpose in clarifying the effects of online sellers e-service quality on customer loyalty.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter contained a detailed presentation and discussion of data analysis and the findings from 100 questionnaires completed by customers that buy online in Cabiao, Nueva Ecija. The survey's collected data was tabulated and supported by relevant theoretical underpinnings, interpretations, and implications.

Table 1

Respondent Level of Agreement on the E-Service Quality of Online Sellers.

Respondent Level of Agreement on the E-Service Quality of Online Sellers	WM	VI
Efficiency	4.10	Agree
Reliability	4.02	Agree
Fulfillment & Responsiveness	3.89	Agree
Flexibility	3.91	Agree
Privacy	4.14	Agree
Overall	4.01	Agree

Legend: Strongly Agree; 4.21 - 5.00, Agree; 4.20 - 3.41, Somewhat Agree; 3.40 - 2.61, Disagree; 2.60 - 1.81, Strongly Disagree; 1.80 - 1.00

Table 1 summary of the level of agreement with each statement about the quality of e-services offered by online sellers. An overall weighted mean of 4.01 was found, which means "Agree." In terms of efficiency, the respondents agreed with a weighted mean of 4.10. In the term of reliability, respondents was agreed with a weighted mean of 4.02. In terms of fulfillment and responsiveness, the respondents agreed with a weighted mean of 3.89. In terms of flexibility, the respondents agreed with a weighted mean of 3.91. In terms of privacy, the respondents agreed with a weighted mean of 4.14.

Table 2

Degree of Respondent Agreement on Customer Loyalty to the Online Seller

Degree of Respondent Agreement on Customer Loyalty to the Online Seller	WM	VI
Customer loyalty	3.85	Agree
Overall	3.85	Agree

Legend: Strongly Agree; 4.21 - 5.00, Agree; 4.20 - 3.41, Somewhat Agree; 3.40 - 2.61, Disagree; 2.60 - 1.81, Strongly Disagree; 1.80 - 1.00

Table 2 presented the respondents' level of agreement on customer loyalty toward online sellers, with an overall weighted mean of 3.85, which corresponds to "Agree."

Table 3

Factors Related to E-Service Quality of Online Sellers

INDICATORS	P-VALUE	DECISION	CONCLUSION
Efficiency	< .001	Reject Ho	Significant
Reliability	< .001	Reject Ho	Significant
Fulfilment & Responsiveness	< .001	Reject Ho	Significant
Flexibility	< .001	Reject Ho	Significant
Privacy	< .001	Reject Ho	Significant
Overall	< .001	Reject Ho	Significant

Legend: If P-Value=<0.05–Reject Ho (Significant); If P-Value>0.05–Accept Ho (Not Significant)

Table 3 presented the result revealed that the factors related to the e-service quality of online sellers, including efficiency ($p < 0.001$), reliability ($p < 0.001$), Fulfilment and Responsiveness ($p < 0.001$), flexibility ($p < 0.001$), and Privacy ($p < 0.001$), were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). It has led to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0) for each of these factors, as they significantly influence customer loyalty. The results show that all aspects of the quality of an e-service are essential for keeping customers coming back to online sellers. All of the factors were statistically significant, so we can say that the quality of the e-service offered by online sellers is a key factor in customer loyalty.

4. Conclusion

These conclusions are based from the results shown above:

4.1. The respondents agreed with the customer's perception on the e-service quality of online sellers in terms of Efficiency, Reliability, Fulfilment and Responsiveness, Flexibility, and Privacy.

4.2. The respondents agreed that the customer loyalty affects the online sellers' e-service quality

4.3. There was a moderately strong and significant positive correlation between the customers' perception on the e-service quality of online sellers and Customer Loyalty.

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